

EU research project SARAH: ditching tests and simulation of real aircraft geometries

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EU research project SARAHA: ditching tests and simulation of real aircraft geometries

SARAHA (Increased safety and robust certification for ditching of aircrafts and helicopters) is a EU funded research project that has devoted part of its activities to perform experimental guided ditching tests with high horizontal speed (up to 46 m/s). Data obtained from these tests can be used, directly or indirectly, to validate numerical tools and analytical theories for solving the fluid-structure behaviour during ditching. The high speed ditching tests are performed at the facilities of the CNR-INM in Rome and consist in three blocks:

- Determination of Hydrodynamics phenomena at the rear fuselage:
Double curvature rigid specimen
- Determination of fluid-structure interaction on flexible structures:
Aircraft-like structure
- Determination of rupture onset of metallic thin flat plates.

This paper focuses in already available results from these tests and establishes comparison with current Airbus DS Military Aircraft ditching numerical simulation methodology. Measured deformations on flexible structures are very valuable for the validation of ditching structural response obtained from numerical simulation. In addition, all this data will be of significant help for any researcher developing numerical tools or addressing background theories that could be contrasted against these experimental results.

Keywords: structural dynamics; dynamic loads; ditching loads.

Introduction

At Airbus Defence and Space (Aeroelasticity and Structural Dynamics department of Military Transport Aircraft division) ditching has been a topic of continuous research for almost 15 years [1-9]. This interest has also been shared by universities, research laboratories and industrial partners that gathered together in the consortia of the European funded research project SMAES (SMart Aircraft in Emergency Situation, 2011-2014) and, currently, in SARAHA (Increased SAFety and Robust certification for ditching of Aircrafts and Helicopters), which has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 724139.

SARAH has considered the main aspects in a ditching scenario (i.e. a planned emergency landing on water):

- Aircraft conditions before impact (approach phase).
- Structural response during the impact (fluid-structure interaction).
- Sliding of the aircraft until complete stoppage (landing phase).
- Subsequent floatation and evacuation phase.

Figure 1: Ditching Phases

with the main objectives of:

- improving aircraft certification tools to deliver accurate ditching loads for design
- using these methods to analyse and optimize approach, impact, landing and floatation phases to support the pilot in water-landing scenarios.

SARAH has devoted part of its activities to perform experimental guided ditching tests with high horizontal speed (up to 46 m/s). Resulting data can be used, directly or indirectly, to validate numerical tools and analytical theories for solving the fluid-structure behaviour during ditching. The tests are performed at the facilities of the Italian CNR-INM institute in Rome.

Figure 2 Schematic sketch of the guided ditching test setup.

The paper will give an overview of the SARAH project, giving a briefly description of the tests set up and execution. These high horizontal speed guided ditching tests consist on three different blocks:

- Hydrodynamics phenomena at the rear fuselage: different double curvature specimens (representing rear lower fuselage shapes of typical transport and commercial aircraft) will be tested to analyse the effects of fuselage shape on ditching loads and

hydrodynamics.

— Fluid-structure interaction on flexible structures: an aircraft-like aluminium structure, with common structural reinforcement elements present in an aircraft rear lower fuselage (spars, frames and stringers), is used to measure the structural response of a flexible reinforced aeronautical structure.

— Determination of rupture onset: damage and rupture characterization of a flat plate, due to the high pressure loading during ditching, will be investigated (referred as “ditching ballistic limit”).

Test measurements include strains, pressures, forces etc.

The bulky part of the paper focuses in available results from these tests, showing the main trends with the different parameters (i.e. horizontal speed and pitch angle). Part of this information (especially time histories of pressures distributions) can be used directly in ditching analysis. Test results on flexible structures (in particular, measured strains on the specimens) are very valuable for the validation of ditching structural response obtained from numerical simulation. In addition, the resultant data will be of significant help for any researcher developing numerical tools or addressing background theories that could be contrasted against these experimental results.

Concluding remarks will highlight how these results constitute a significant step forward in the understanding of the complex fluid-structure phenomena and subsequent structural response that takes place during a ditching. The paper will include suggestions for further work in this area.

SARAH project overview

The European Funded Research Project SARAH (Increased SAfety and Robust certification for ditching of Aircrafts and Helicopters, European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 724139) aims to establish novel holistic, simulation-based approaches for the analysis of aircraft and helicopter ditching. SARAH project will tackle the following objectives:

- Improve aircraft/ helicopter certification tools in order to deliver accurate loads to safely design aircrafts/ helicopters and deliver input on how ditching needs to be simulated in order to obtain robust, safe and accurate loading information

- Derive a robust way to safely design new configurations (for which no engineering experience is available) w.r.t. ditching
- Use methods obtained to analyse and optimise approach, landing and impact phases to supporting the pilot in water-landing scenarios

SARAH project is composed from a consortium of 12 partners including experts from original equipment manufacturer (OEM) industries, experienced suppliers of simulation technologies, established academic and research institution and supported by representatives of the certification authorities.

At Airbus Defence and Space, the specific challenge for the design of airborne vehicles is to minimize the risk of injury to persons on board during the whole water landing and to give chance for safe evacuation of the occupants. The developments within SARAH (including elasticity effects obtained from the test campaign) will enable a deeper knowledge of the two-way interaction between structural deformation and hydrodynamic loads.

SARAH high-speed ditching test summary

Ditching test installation

The High Speed Ditching (HSD) facility was developed during FP7-SMAES EU funded research project. During high speed ditching tests, specimens are mounted to a trolley, which is accelerated with elastic ropes towards a water basin along a 64 m guide, reaching horizontal speeds of up to 46 m/s. The guide can be rotated to adjust the vertical to horizontal speed ratio between 0.03 and 0.05. Figure 3 shows the trolley, acquisition box and a double curvature specimen (left), and an instance after impact on water during a ditching test (right).

Figure 3. SARAH High speed ditching (HSD) facility at CNR-INM

Ditching test execution

During the complete execution of each run test, six phases could be identified:

Figure 4: Phases of each ditching test run

- (1) Release
- (2) Acceleration: 1.00 s approximately
- (3) Constant velocity: 0.20 s approximately
- (4) Impact and natural deceleration: 0.30 s approximately
- (5) Forced breaking: 0.44 s approximately
- (6) Stop

From the structure point of view, all the relevant phenomena occur during test impact phase in a time interval starting when the panel trailing edge gets in contact with the water surface (t_{TE}) and ending when the panel gets fully submerged (t_{LE}). The test results after t_{LE} are not considered representative of a ditching event in an aircraft, so they have not been taken into account for the analysis.

Figure 5: SMAES photos illustrating the guiding structure, the trolley and the specimen at impact phase.

High-Speed ditching tests for determination of Hydrodynamics phenomena at the rear fuselage

High speed ditching tests for double-curvature (longitudinal and transversal curvature) rigid specimens of three representative fuselage shapes have been defined for these tests with the objective of analysing the effects of fuselage shape on ditching loads and hydrodynamics.

Figure 6 shows the three fuselage shapes, as well as the location of the double-curvature rigid specimen (portion of the lower rear fuselage, 1240 mm long and 660 mm wide) that were manufactured for these tests:

Figure 6. SARAH fuselage shapes and double-curvature portion used for the high-speed ditching tests

- SP1: to test airliner shape ditching impacts at high pitch angles.
- SP1B: to test airliner shape ditching impacts at low pitch angles.
- SP2: to test business jet shape ditching impacts at any pitch angle.
- SP3: to test transport aircraft shape ditching impacts at any pitch angle.

Test conditions varied individual parameters (pitch, horizontal velocity and vertical/horizontal velocity ratio) for each of the fuselage shapes. Specimens were manufactured in high density foam, and instrumented with 30 pressure probes (see Figure 7). Load cells between the specimen and the trolley measured longitudinal and normal loads. Data was acquired unfiltered at 200 kHz. External and underwater high-speed cameras recorded the event kinematics.

Figure 7. Distribution of the pressure probes in the double curvature specimen

A total of 63 ditching tests were completed. A vast amount of experimental data was produced, which is currently under analysis, and final conclusions have not yet been established. However, some preliminary inferences have been made based on repeatedly observed phenomena.

Results from the three fuselage shapes tested have been compared for horizontal speed 40 m/s, vertical speed -1.5 m/s and pitch 6 degrees test conditions (specimen S1B was used for these conditions with fuselage shape 1) and are shown in Figure 8 and Figure 10. These figures show the pressure time histories for the transducers located on the symmetry plane for the area located rearward and forward of the point of initial impact, respectively.

Vertical bars in the plots indicate the time at which the specimen's leading/trailing edge immersion (LEI/TEI) probably occurred. This time of immersion is obtained from the ratio of the Z-coordinate from the first point of water contact to the leading, or trailing edge, and the vertical velocity. Note that, taking into account geometrical shapes and this test conditions, first impact occurred close to probe location 21 for specimen SP1B and close to probe location 17 for both, SP2 and SP3

Following differences between the three fuselage shapes can be highlighted from the information in Figure 8 and Figure 10:

- Rearward of the initial impact point (suction area) [10]:

Figure 8. Comparison of measured ditching pressures (suction area) for the three fuselage shapes **SP1B**, **SP2** and **SP3**. $V_x=40\text{m/s}$, $V_z=-1.5\text{m/s}$, pitch 6 degrees.

- SP1 does not present any cavitation before the leading or trailing edges have immersed.
- Fuselage shapes SP2 and SP3 show cavitation (drop of pressure to negative value) and ventilation (later arise of pressure to 0) at every probe rearwards of the point of impact.
- SP2 drops the pressure rapidly to cavitation, with no positive pressure.
- SP3 presents a positive initial region (more prominent for probe location 17) that suddenly drops to cavitation after around 8 ms.

Figure 9. Cavitation (left) and ventilation (right) phenomena during a 34.5 m/s horizontal speed ditching test on a double curvature specimen

- Forward of the initial impact point (overpressure area):

Figure 10. Comparison of measured ditching pressures (overpressure area) for the three fuselage shapes **SP1B**, **SP2** and **SP3**. $V_x=40\text{m/s}$, $V_z=-1.5\text{m/s}$, pitch 6 degrees.

- Pressure peaks for shapes SP2 and SP3 happen nearly simultaneous, with a small time delay (0.5-2 ms) for SP2. Peak values are much larger (30-85%) for SP3 fuselage than for SP2. The decay of pressure is longer for SP3 than for SP2 (it takes more time to drop the pressure). Final pressure is also larger for SP3 (45-80%).
- Pressure peaks for shape SP1 are of the same order than SP2, especially for pressure probe 24 and forward. In the case of SP1, due to the specimen geometrical characteristics, the phenomena is faster, with a time advance of approximately 20 ms.
- Consequently, loads for fuselage shape SP3 are larger (40%) than for SP2, as seen in Figure 11. It is also observed that fuselage shape SP1 shows a small measured value of the vertical load, which is still under further investigation.

Figure 11. Comparison of measured ditching reaction loads for three fuselage shapes.

Tests: **SP1B**, **SP2** and **SP3**. $V_x=40\text{m/s}$, $V_z=-1.5\text{m/s}$, pitch 6 degrees.

In order to have a deeper insight of the effects of adding longitudinal curvature to the problem, the results on the overpressure zone of the double-curvature ditching tests for the fuselage shape SP3 have been compared with the results from the SMAES testing campaign [11] were simpler geometries, flat plate and single-curvature rigid positive curvature (convex, only transversal curvature) specimens, were tested. Figure 12 presents the time histories of every pressure probe available for each test.

Figure 12. Pressure time histories for flat plate (top), single convex curvature (centre) and double-curvature shape SP3 (bottom) ditching tests at $V_x=40\text{m/s}$, $V_z=-1.5\text{m/s}$, pitch 6 degrees.

Figure 13 shows the location of the pressure probes in the rigid specimens tested in SMAES.

Figure 13. Pressure transducer locations in SMAES flat and curved rigid specimens [11]

Figure 12 show similar behaviour for fuselage shape SP3 and positively curved (convex) specimens of SMAES: attenuation of the peak pressure values towards the sides (along the Y-axis), more pronounced in SP3 for the probes positioned in the straight section (P18 onwards).

Effect of longitudinal curvature can be obtained by comparing test results at similar pressure probe locations on the specimen. In particular, Figure 14 presents a comparison of the different specimen configurations on pressure probes along the symmetry plane, for peak and final pressures values.

Figure 14. Peak pressure (left) and final pressure (right) for double-curvature SP3 (red), flat (green) and single curvature convex (blue) rigid specimens ditching tests at $V_x=40\text{m/s}$, $V_z=-1.5\text{m/s}$ and pitch=6deg

Following conclusions can be derived from the results in Figure 14:

- At the centreline, peak pressure of flat plat and convex single-curvature is of similar magnitude.
- Fuselage shape SP3 showed a considerable attenuation (>38%) of the peak pressures closer to the point of first water contact ($x=0m$), with a smaller, but perceivable reduction ($\approx 12\%$), in the peak pressure for next position ($x=0.09m$) has. The region of attenuation coincides with the area where there is variation on local pitch angle.
- In terms of final pressure, the three geometries show similar values for probes forward of the initial water contact region. However, for P17, which is very close to the initial impact, the final pressure shows cavitation (≈ -100 kPa). Therefore, P17 is in a critical position where initially it will perceive positive pressure, which will transition to negative and cavitation. However, this is only true for this specific case.

High-Speed ditching tests for determination of fluid-structure interaction on flexible structures

These tests were designed to investigate the deformations of an aircraft-like structure during a ditching event. A single curvature fuselage specimen (600 x 1200 mm dimensions, 2 m radius) with two frames and four stringers was constructed with typical aircraft thicknesses and materials.

The tests will be performed at the HSD facility at a horizontal speed of 45 m/s, a vertical speed of -1.5 m/s, and a pitch angle of 6 deg. Four specimens, with two different skin thicknesses (1.2 and 1.6 mm), were built and instrumented with 30 strain gauges spread along the skin and stringers. The figure below shows the first specimen to be tested. Load cells will register normal and transverse reaction forces. External and submerged high-speed cameras will record the event.

Figure 15. Aircraft-like structure specimen for high speed ditching test

Even though tests of this type had not started at the time of this publication, preliminary explicit simulations were executed with PAM-CRASH solver to predict the outcome of the tests.

A finite element (FE) model was developed from a geometry model provided by the specimen manufacturer. 122 components were discretized into about 117,000 shell elements of 5 mm average size and joint with fastener joints (PLINK). The synthetic pressures methodology [4,6] was introduced to simulate the ditching pressure loads.

Figure 16. SARAH fuselage-like tests specimen FE Mode: Skin deformed shape with Synthetic Pressures applied ($V_x=46\text{m/s}$, Pitch 6 deg, $t=0.05\text{s}$)

The results of the simulations predict large buckling-like deformations of the forward frame. A small increase in the ditching speed produced the collapse of the structure. Therefore it was concluded prior to tests that the conditions would produce loads close to structural failure. However, these are pre-test simulations, which are by design conservative, and might be over predicting structural deformation. The figure below shows the effective plastic strain sustained by the virtual specimen under simulated ditching loads.

Figure 17. Permanent deformations on the fuselage-like structure ditching test predicted by explicit finite element simulations

High-Speed ditching tests for determination of rupture onset of metallic thin plate:

This part of SARAH test campaign, already ongoing, is aimed to determine the “ballistic limit”/rupture onset of very thin aluminium 2024-T3 flat panels (0.4 to 0.8 mm) under ditching loads. The trigger of these tests was the results obtained with thin aluminium plates (0.8mm) from SMAES, where it was shown quite large deformation on the panels, but still far from any failure condition.

The test sequence started with the thinnest available panel (0.4 mm). Figure 18 shows the decision tree used for this testing procedure, in green the completed tests.

Figure 18. SARAH rupture onset tests sequence decision tree

The thin flat aluminium plate (646x1240 mm) was bolted to a rigid steel frame (85 mm all around), and launched at highest available speed (horizontal 45 m/s and vertical -1.5 m/s) with high pitch angle (10-16 degrees). Between the plate and the frame there is a 3 mm reinforcement aluminium plate all around (leaving a 276x870 mm window on the thin plate). Two options for the bonding of this reinforcement to the thin plate, with different purposes, have been considered during the definition of these tests (Figure 19):

- Option A: Adhesive between reinforcement and thin plate only at area covered by the frame. This configuration is intended to obtain the desired mode of failure (a longitudinal crack along the panel, produced by membrane stresses in the panel).
- Option B: Adhesive between reinforcement and thin plate at area covered by the reinforcement. This secondary bonding method was designed to constrain the specimen panel to a reinforcement plate, and consequently to trigger failure of the thin panel on the corners of the reinforcement.

Figure 19. SARAH thin panel bonding area to reinforcement plate

These tests were not instrumented due to the risk of water damage to the on-board acquisition system. However, high-speed cameras recorded from the exterior and underwater, and a laser scanner was used to capture the post-test permanent deformation of the panel, ruptured or not.

Differences on test results, when using these two options for the bonding, are highlighted in next paragraphs. Comparison with a PAM-CRASH explicit dynamic finite element (FE) pre-test simulation is established: the specimen panel and reinforcement panel were modelled with an average element size of 5 mm. The steel frame was simplified to a rigid surface, where the panel was bolted to using connection PLINK elements. Synthetic pressures methodology [4, 6] was applied to the panel.

Figure 20 shows test results on a thin aluminium plate with bonding Option A: the permanently deformed panel was laser scanned while still attached to the steel frame. The maximum measured out-of-plane deformation of the test specimen was of 57.8 mm.

Figure 20. Permanent deformation on 0.4 mm aluminium plate. Test results:
 $V_x=46.7\text{m/s}$, $V_z=-1.56\text{m/s}$, Pitch=10deg. (Source:CNR-INM)

Figure 21 shows an overlap of 3D scanned test result (transparent grey) and simulation (coloured) results. The simulation results achieve a very high level of correlation. The peak deformation predicted by the simulation is of 55.6 mm, which is just a 3.8% smaller than the test results.

Figure 21. Test vs simulation comparison of the permanent deformation on a 0.4 mm aluminum panel result of ditching loads. $V_x=46.7\text{m/s}$, $V_z=-1.56\text{m/s}$, Pitch=10deg.

Figure 22 shows the test results on a thin aluminium plate with bonding Option B: The panel thickness and test conditions were identical to those shown in Figure 20, but in this case, the panel failed as shown in Figure 22. The damage was initiated in the area of the thin panel at the bottom corners of the reinforcement panel. The crack then propagated to the centre of the panel, and longitudinally towards the opposite end. The panel was fully de-bonded from the reinforcement area.

Figure 22. Failed 0.4 mm aluminium panel after ditching test at 45 m/s horizontal and - 1.5 m/s vertical speed, at 10 deg pitch. (Source: CNR-INM)

Pre-test simulation predicted the panel failure initiation, as shown in Figure 23. The left image shows a snapshot of the underwater high speed video, at the instant when fracture was initiated. The right image shows the effective plastic deformation of the panel, with a scale from 0.01% (blue) to ultimate effective plastic strain (red). It can be seen that the first elements erode in the same area where failure was initiated in the test.

Figure 23. Moment of fracture initiation of a 0.4 mm aluminium panel during a ditching test from an underwater high speed camera view (left) and the predicted results on a FE simulation with the synthetic pressures (right)

As a conclusion, it has been demonstrated that pre-test FE Model simulations, with synthetic pressure methodology [4,6] applied, were able to accurately predict the structural deformation and failure of very thin aluminium panels due to high speed ditching loads. The complete set of ongoing tests will be used as a validation point of the synthetic pressure methodology with deformable structures.

Concluding remarks and future activities

The paper has presented the experimental guided ditching tests with high horizontal speed (up to 46 m/s) that are being performed as part of the activities in SARAH EU funded research project. The high speed ditching tests are performed at the facilities of the CNR-INM in Rome and consist in three main blocks:

1. High-Speed ditching tests for determination of Hydrodynamics phenomena at the rear fuselage: double-curvature specimens.

Two main effects have been highlighted:

- Longitudinal curvature effect: Rearwards of the initial impact point (suction area) hydrodynamic phenomena of cavitation and ventilation have been measured, especially for fuselage shapes with sudden change in longitudinal curvature (SP2 and SP3). Forwards of the initial impact point (overpressure area) at the centreline, tests with fuselage shape SP3 showed a considerable attenuation (>38%) of the peak pressures, closer to the point of first water contact, that arises to peak pressure values comparable to the ones measured on SMAES flat plates in the region where the curvature is constant. Consequently, it can be assumed that the local pitch angle has an important effect in local peak pressure loads and transition to cavitation.

- Transverse curvature has a strong influence on the peak pressure. Shape 3 tests show an attenuation of the peak pressure values towards the sides (along the Y-axis). Even more pronounced for the probes positioned in the straight section (P18 onwards). Similar results were obtained for single curvature tests from SMAES.

Consequently, it is clear that both longitudinal and transverse curvature induce important effects on the local pressures acting on the fuselage's surface. The definition of the synthetic pressures should be adjusted to account for these (alleviating) local effects on ditching loads.

2. High-Speed ditching tests for determination of fluid-structure interaction on flexible structures: Fuselage-like specimen.

These tests were designed to investigate the deformations of an aircraft-like structure during a ditching event. A single curvature fuselage specimen (600 x 1200 mm dimensions, 2 m radius) with two frames and four stringers was constructed with typical aircraft thicknesses and materials. The tests will be performed at the HSD facility and

will be instrumented with 30 strain gauges (numerical simulation has been used to position these strain gauges).

Measured deformations on this flexible structure will be used for the validation of ditching structural response obtained from numerical simulation.

3. High-Speed ditching tests for determination of rupture onset of metallic thin plate.

It has been show that pre-test FE Model simulations, with synthetic pressure methodology [4,6] applied, were able to accurately predict the structural deformation and failure of very thin aluminium panels due to high speed ditching loads. The complete set of ongoing tests will be used as a validation point of the synthetic pressure methodology with deformable structures.

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